

Fundamental Insights of Malnutrition in India

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India is now facing very serious problems like childhood malnutrition. India is continuously working and getting success in various fields like economics, export, startups, businesses, and technology, etc. But still, India is having the highest child malnutrition in the world. Malnutrition is of various types like underweight, overweight, stunted growth of children, and so on. The government is starting many programs and schemes to tackle such types of problems but as per the expectations, it is not working. According to data provided by 'Food and Nutrition Security Analysis, India, 2019' report authored by the Government of India there is a small improvement but it's not sufficient to complete the target of "Zero Hunger" and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), By 2030, end all forms of malnutrition, including achieving by 2025, the internationally agreed targets on stunting and wasting in children under 5 years of age. The government of India is taking different initiatives to reduce malnutrition like Integrated Child Development Services (ICDS) especially for lactating and pregnant mothers and children, National Rural Health Mission (NRHM), Mid-Day Meal Scheme (MDM), National Food Security Mission, etc.

Keywords: Malnutrition, economic, Child Malnutrition, hunger.

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Introduction

The total number of wasted children under age 5 is 49.48 million; this becomes 49 million when rounded to the nearest integer, and 49.5 million when rounded to the nearest tenth (1) It is also observed that the malnutrition problem in India is a serious issue that is a relatively small number of states, districts, and villages account for a large share of the malnutrition burden — only 5 states and 50% of villages account for about 80% of the malnutrition burden (2). World Bank data indicates that India has one of the world’s highest demographics of children suffering from malnutrition – said to be double that of Sub-Saharan Africa with dire consequences. India’s Global Hunger Index India ranking of 67 the 80 nations with the worst hunger situation places us even below North Korea or Sudan. 44% of children under the age of 5 are underweight, while 72% of infants have anemia. One in every five Indians (both genders) is too thin with a BMI of less than 18.5, while every fourth male and second female are anemic. The NFHS-4 highlighted that one in three women consume dark green leafy vegetables, chicken/meat/fish/eggs only once a week while one in two women do not consume fruits even once a week. The NFHS report also noted that one in five women, however, consumes aerated drinks weekly, one in 10 women consumes fried food daily. Only one in 10 children aged 6-23 months receive an adequate diet (3). As per 2001 report, 99 % of total death of children all over the world belongs to the economically middle class and lower-class families (3).

Malnutrition problem in Western Rajasthan: children from private school

Malnutrition problem in Western Rajasthan: from government school

The dietary assessment showed that nutrient intake of iron, β-carotene, calcium, zinc and vitamin C in children was found to be low as compared to the daily nutrient recommendation for the age group. This implied that children may have micronutrient deficiencies which could be a serious issue. Thus, it results that rural influence, lower socio-economic condition, higher birth order, lower birth interval, maternal health, the literacy level of parents, agricultural diversity, and faulty feeding habits have adverse effects on the nutritional status of children. So accordingly, different Policies should be executed to educate parents and other child caregivers to effectively utilize the available food resources and fostering practices to improve the nutritional status of their pre-school children.

There are many factors which are responsible for influencing malnutrition problem as if a woman during her pregnancy is suffering from underweight, anemia and several nutritional deficiencies automatically abnormal conditions will observe in her baby like underweight baby, fetus mortality, stunted growth and many more. In this case, various reasons are involved like uneducated parents, unawareness about the things like family planning, nutritional feeding. The second important reason is the economical factor, which is going to effects a lot because of poverty they not able to take proper care of children and not able to give sufficient food to their children due to a greater number of family members. Currently, there are many food products with high nutrition, long shelf life with various flavors are available on market. But due to the high cost and unawareness of such products, everyone cannot afford to buy this also.

Conclusion

The main reason for the malnutrition, first one is Economical aspect, as data represented by

Various institutions economical background of the family is more important. Malnutrition problem is seen very high in rural areas than the urban cities, Government school than the private school and poor families than the rich families. Slums and different tribal communities faced this problem Because of economic conditions only. These communities are not able to afford such products because of high cost only even though it has high nutrition. The solution to this problem is to provide protein, iron, and fiber-rich product at low cost so that poor people can afford that product. Some institutions are working on this. A second and most important reason is awareness, now a day's government and private organizations are working with an aim to resolve problems like overweight, overweight, stunted growth of children. Integrated Child Development Services (ICDS), National Rural Health Mission (NRHM), Mid-Day Meal Scheme (MDM), National Food Security Mission, etc. these are the initiatives taken by the government. Different Anganwadi centers providing food to children and also pregnant and lactating women, which involves protein, iron, and different vitamins, and mineral-rich ingredients. Only because of lack of awareness among people they suffer through this problem. To tackle the problem of malnutrition there is maximum awareness is needed which will help to reduce problems related to child health. Mother's health is equally important because a healthy mother will give birth to a Healthy Child. Hence equal focus and programmers related to pregnant and lactating women are important. As well as sanitation, hygiene, feeding process to child contribute equally to the health of the child.

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